

Hospital data analytics for Business Intelligence- an analytical tool for patient feedback analysis

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Abstract: Big data is a term that describes large, hard-to-manage volumes of data – both structured and unstructured – that swamp businesses on a day-to-day basis. But it's not just the type or amount of data that's important, it's what organizations do with the data that matters. Data analytics is the science of analysing raw data to make conclusions about that information. Many of the techniques and processes of data analytics have been automated into mechanical processes and algorithms that work over raw data for human consumption .Analytics is the systematic computational analysis of data or statistics. It is used for the discovery, interpretation, and communication of meaningful patterns in data. It also entails applying data patterns towards effective decision-making. In this paper we are trying to understand big data challenges, what exactly data science is and what do data scientists do. Also we studied about how data science is contrasted with other discipline like machine learning, computation science, data analysis, traditional software delivery, scientific computing, data engineering etc. We analysed some case studies and use cases. We analysed application of big data analysis in Stanford Medicine together with Google cloud platform to support with precision health and more efficient patient care. Another case study in the field of cancer research, which require huge amount of data processing, is also analysed in this paper IoT devices are used in a wide range of businesses and industries which result in large quantities of diverse data. Billions of real time data are collected in IoT devices. Big data analysis is helping to make sense of this data.

Key Words: Data Science, Health care, Big Data.

1. INTRODUCTION:

Data Science is an area that manages, manipulates, extracts, and interprets knowledge from tremendous amount of data. Data science is a multidisciplinary field of study with goal to address the challenges in big data. Data science principles apply to all data – big and small. Theories and techniques from many fields and disciplines are used to investigate and

analyse a large amount of data to help decision makers in many industries such as science, engineering, economics, politics, finance, and education. Data science is an interdisciplinary field that uses scientific methods, processes, algorithms and systems to extract knowledge and insights from noisy, structured and unstructured data, and apply knowledge and actionable insights from data across a broad range of application domain.

Big Data are data sets so large or so complex that traditional methods of storing, accessing, and analyzing is difficult. Bigdata is a collection of data that is huge in size and is growing exponentially with time. Big Data analytics examples includes stock exchanges, social media sites, jet engines, etc. However, there is a lot of potential value hidden in this data, so organizations are eager to harness it to drive innovation and competitive advantage. Big Data technologies and approaches are used to drive value out of data rich environments in ways that traditional analytics tools and methods cannot.

2. MACHINE LEARNING VS DATA SCIENCE

By using Machine learning we can Develop new individual models .By using datascience we can explore many models, build and tune hybrids. Machine learning prove mathematical properties of models ,but data science understand empirical properties or statistical properties of models. Machine learning Improve/validate on a few, relatively clean, small datasets. Data science Develop/use tools that can handle big datasets.

Fig 1. Machine Learning

Fig 2: Data Science

3. DATA SCIENCE & ACADEMIA

According to Alex Szalay, these sorts of researchers must be "Pi-shaped" as opposed to the more traditional "T-shaped" researcher. In his opinion, a classic PhD program generates T-shaped researchers: scientists with wide-but-shallow general knowledge, but deep skill and expertise in one particular area. The new breed of scientific researchers, the data scientists, must be Pi-shaped: that is, they maintain the same wide breadth, but push deeper both in their own subject area and in the statistical or computational methods that help drive modern research:

Fig. 3:T shaped and Pi shaped knowledge.

4. DATA SCIENCE APPLICATIONS

a. Business: In business such as machine design to banking to food delivery, data science is used to enhance their operations and to satisfy their customers.

b. Health Care

The great advances in information technology helps a lot in health care .By using these technologies health records can be maintained electronically in an efficient way.By analysing health data of an individual over a long duration clinicians can identify patterns hidden in the data and compute the chance of an individual patient for a medical complication in near future.

5. DATA SCIENCE: CASE STUDY

a. Health Care in Stanford Medicine.

Stanford Medicine and Google are working together to transform patient care and medical research through data science. .Stanford Medicine will use the power, security and scale of Google Cloud Platform to support precision health and more efficient patient care. Stanford’s forthcoming Clinical Genomics Service, which puts genomic sequencing into the hands of clinicians to help diagnose disease, will be built using Google Genomics, a service that applies the same technologies that power Google Search and Maps to securely store, process, explore and share genomic data sets.

b. Cancer Research

Cancer is a disease caused when cells divide uncontrollably and spread into surrounding tissues.It is a very complex disease; a single tumor can have more than 100 billion cells, and each cell can acquire mutations individually. The disease is always changing, evolving, and adapting. In the field of cancer study we can employ the power of big data analytics and high-performance computing.

c. Internet of Things (IoT)

The Internet of Things is rapidly growing. The Internet of Things (IOT) will soon produce a massive volume and variety of data at unprecedented velocity. If "Big Data" is the product of the IOT, "Data Science" is it's soul.

6. CONCLUSION

In this paper we have analysed what exactly is Data Science and what do Data Scientists do.

Not every thing with data or science is Data Science. Data science is rooted in solid foundations of mathematics and statistics, computer science, and domain knowledge. Also what Data Science contrasted with other disciplines like machine learning, academia. Also we studied application of data science in health care, and business. We also studied case studies in Stanford medicine , cancer studies and internet of things.

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